

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

FLT1

(fms related receptor tyrosine kinase 1)

A Target Enabling Package (TEP)

Gene ID / UniProt ID / EC	2321/ P17948
Target Nominator	TREAT-AD, AMP-AD
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CONTENTS OF TEP

Bioinformatic analysis: Target source & hypothesis

Protein constructs & expression methods: **FLT1C-c201:** Ig-like domain of Human FLT1 (E27-E748). Contains a C-terminal 6His and AviTag (allowing in vitro biotinylation, if needed). Protein produced in Expi293F cells.

TARGET SOURCE & HYPOTHESIS

Why was the target selected? This target is found within a TMT proteomics network module that was highly correlated with cognition. This module (Module 42) contains several novel AD targets, including SMOC1 and SFRP1.

TREAT-AD Target Risk Score: 3.46 (rank #2174, 91.3th percentile)

The TREAT-AD Center has developed a target ranking score encompassing genomics and genetics evidence. The Target Risk Score represents the gene target's general relevance to Alzheimer's Disease, and is the sum of the target's Genetics Score and Genomics Score. Target Risk Score values range from 0 to 5, with 5 being evidence of the strongest association with AD. A complete description of the methodology used to calculate these scores is available [here](#). This score was taken from Agora, Data Version syn13363290-v62.

The TREAT-AD Target Risk Score for this target is 3.46 out of 5 (rank #2174, 91.3th percentile). The individual score components include 1.46 of 3 for genetics, and 1.997 out of 2 for genomics. The meta-analysis of proteomic and transcriptomic data sources used in the genomics score indicates that the expression of FLT1, both protein and RNA, is significantly increased in brains from patients with AD.

The TREAT-AD Center has also developed a target categorization system specific to AD relevant processes, termed biological domains (biodomains). These biological domains are defined by constituent Gene Ontology (GO) terms and genes are then annotated to specific biological domains via GO term annotations. FLT1 is annotated to GO terms from the Vasculature, Structural Stabilization, Synapse, Immune Response, and Endolysosome domains.

Overall	rank	pctl	GeneticsScore	OmicsScore
3.455	2174	91.29	1.458	1.997

Cell-type specific expression is assessed using single-cell expression data from the Seattle Alzheimer's Disease Brain Cell Atlas (SEA-AD). The distribution of expression values for all genes found in each broad cell type are displayed as violins. The expression of the target in subtypes within each broad class is shown as a point. Blue points show the summary expression of cells from individuals with no dementia, while red points show summary metrics of cells from dementia patients. Open circles reflect low confidence measures of expression.

The expression of FLT1 is confidently detected in endothelial, vascular and leptomenigeal cells (VLMC), as well as microglia from dementia patients within this dataset.

SUMMARY OF PROJECT

The FLT1 project is based upon the science discussed in the next section and its discovery within a proteomic module heavily linked to AD cognitive decline and pathological progression (1). The goal of this project is to develop and share a basic target enabling package (TEP) for the angiogenic FLT1 tyrosine

kinase receptor that can be shared with the scientific community. The FLT1 TEP consists of identified and validated antibodies for histological and biochemical uses, purified proteins, a full bioinformatic characterization, and other useful reagents described above. TREAT-AD promotes these resources for free use in the hope that these tools will facilitate a future characterization of FLT1 by the AD scientific community.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

FLT1, fms related receptor tyrosine kinase 1, also known as VEGFR1, is a receptor tyrosine kinase that is a member of the VEGF ligand binding family (1, 4) that signals by trans-phosphorylation and activation leading to active complex formation with numerous other intracellular signaling moieties, including PLCgamma (2, 3) and activation of the PI3K pathway (4, 5). The extracellular moiety of FLT1 contains the ligand-binding domain comprised of seven immunoglobulin like domains that associates with VEGFA, VEGFB and PGF (3, 6-10). The ligand binding domain is tethered to the transmembrane domain and the tyrosine kinase domain, which resides within the cytoplasmic region (3, 6-10). The extracellular ligand binding domain is cleaved by members of the ADAM family of metalloproteinases (11), which results in the soluble FLT1 (sFLT1) generation that can counter-regulate the membrane associated VEGF-binding receptor family.

The biological role of FLT1 is complicated and developmental stage and context dependent; however, the general function of FLT1 is to stimulate vascular angiogenesis, starting in early development (12), and includes the promotion of neuro-angiogenesis in early developmental stages in brain (13, 14). Despite its general role in developmental angiogenesis, FLT1 inhibition is associated with elevated cognitive function in offspring following maternal prenatal stress (15), suggesting a complex role for FLT1 in regulating brain health that is highly contextual dependent. Further, it may play a neurodegenerative role in some conditions, such as muscular dystrophy (16, 17), in which treatment with the FLT1 antibody facilitates the angiogenesis of muscular tissue in MDX mouse model of MD by blocking VEGF interaction with FLT1—likely shunting VEGF to other VEGFR family members, which drive angiogenic response and support muscle development in this animal model (17).

However, it appears to play a beneficial role in multiple forms of neurological trauma. In acute brain trauma, FLT1 expression is associated with augmented recovery (18), and following toxic insult to hippocampal tissue, which induced edema, FLT1 expression is elevated and promotes recovery (19). In hippocampal ischemia, FLT1 levels are elevated for weeks within reactive astrocytes and microglial, likely to restore vascular perfusion (20-22). Post-stroke ischemia is ameliorated by rapid restoration of vascular perfusion, and pericyte expression of FLT1 attenuates damage following cortical ischemia (23). Additionally, FLT1 facilitates axonal outgrowth in spinal slice cultures, suggesting a general neurotrophic role for the receptor (24), which is consistent with its elevated expression acute trauma within sciatic nerve damage (25).

Angiogenic promotion also is involved in cancer prognosis and progression, and forming tumors require vascularization to grow and metastasize. There is a rich literature showing the role of FLT1 in facilitating tumor growth through angiogenic stimulation (26-28), and consequently, many therapeutic approaches have been developed to target FLT1's oncogenic potential (29-31). Meta-analyses of the clinical cancer trials using receptor tyrosine kinase inhibitors targeted against FLT1 show elevated levels of incidents of neuropathy (32), however, suggesting that while inhibiting FLT1 in one domain may be advantageous, it may be detrimental in others. Given the linkage between vascular viability and neurodegeneration, it is not surprising that FLT1 has been implicated in association with AD (33). The identification of FLT1 for study within our program came from deep proteomic studies of large sets of postmortem brains, and FLT1 was identified within a module that ranked highest for both cognitive decline and pathological association (1). This module was also comprised of a significant fraction of soluble heparin binding protein, and the heparin binding proteome was later implicated in AD pathogenesis (34) independently, consistent with

FLT1's association with its cognate ligands being determined by their heparin binding state (9, 35). The complexities of FLT1's interaction with neurodegeneration warrants further exploration, and we hope the resources that TREAT-AD provide with facilitate that undertaking.

RESULTS – THE TEP

Proteins Purified

1. FLT1C-c201: Ig-like domain of Human FLT1 (E27-E748). Contains a C-terminal 6His and AviTag (allowing in vitro biotinylation, if needed). Protein produced in Expi293F cells.

See **Additional information (section 1)** with details of plasmid expression constructs and purification procedures.

CONCLUSION

The tools presented here provide a foundation for further investigation of the role of FLT1 in AD.

FUNDING INFORMATION

The work performed by the Emory-Sage-SGC TREAT-AD Center has been funded by the National Institute on Aging through grant U54 AG065187.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Materials and Methods

Proteins Expression and Purification

All relevant plasmids are available on addgene: [TREAT-AD plasmid collection](#)

1. FLT1C-c200: Ig-like domain of Human FLT1 (E27-E748). Contains a C-terminal 6His and AviTag (allowing in vitro biotinylation, if needed). Protein produced in Expi293F cells.

Construct ID	FLT1C-c201
Parental vector	pHL-avitag3
Tag	C-terminal His6, C-terminal Avitag
Protein mass (with tag and secretion signal)	89114 Da
Extinction Coefficient ($M^{-1} cm^{-1}$)	89730
Protein sequence (with tag)	MGILPSPGMPALLSLVSLLSVLLMGCVAETGSKLKDPPELSLKGQTQHIMQAGQTLHL QCRGEEAAHKWLSPEMVSKESERLSITKSACGRNGKQFCSTLTLNTAQANHTGFYSC KYLAVPTSKKKETESAIYIFISDTGRPFVEMYSEIPEIIHMTEGRELVIPCRVTSPNITVT LKKFPLDTLIPDGKRRIWDSRKGFIISNATYKEIGLLTCEATVNGHLYKTNLYLTHRQTNT IIDVQISTPRPVKLLRGHTLVLNCTATTPLNTRVQMTWSYPDEKNKRASVRRRIDQS NSHANIFYSVLTIDKMQNKDKGLYTCRVRSGPSFKSVNTSVHIYDKAFITVKHRKQQ VLETVAGKRSYRLSMKVKAFPSPEVVWLKDGLPATEKSARYLTRGYSLIHKDVTEEDA GNYTILLSIKQSNVFNLTATLIVNVKPKIYEKAVSSFPDPALYPLGSRQILTCTAYGIPQ PTIKWFWHPCNHNHSEARCDFCNNEESFILDADSNMGNRIESITQRMAIIIEGKN KMASTLVVADSRISGIYICIASNKVGTVGRNISFYITDVPNGFHVNLKMPTEGEDLK LSCTVNFLYRDVTWILLRVTNNRTMHYSISKQKMAITKEHSITLNLTIMNVS LQDS GTYACRARNVYTGEEILQKKEITIRDQEAPYLLRNLSDHTVAISSSTLDCHANGVPE PQITWFKNNHKIQQEPGIILGPGSSTLFIERVTEEDEGVYHCKATNQKGSVESSAYLT VQGTSDKSNLEGTGGSGGSLNDIFEAQKIEWHEGRTKHHHHHH

Purified Protein	
Size Exclusion Chromatography: FLT1C-c201 (with tag)	
Intact Mass Deconvolution: FLT1C-c201 (with tag)	N/A
Observed Mass:	N/A
Protein yield:	0.4mg/L of culture

Expression and Purification Protocol	
Expression host	<i>Mammalian:</i> Expi293F cells (Thermo Fisher Scientific)

Expression medium	FreeStyle 293 Expression Medium (Thermo Fisher Scientific)
Plasmid purification	Transform the construct into the <i>E. coli</i> strain MACH1. Plate on LB-agar plates containing ampicillin (100 µg/ml). Inoculate 5 ml LB broth containing ampicillin (100 ug/ml) with a single colony and grow 6h at 37°C with shaking. Inoculate 800 ml LB broth containing the same antibiotic with 2 ml of starter culture and grow overnight at 37°C with shaking. Split culture into 4 and perform MaxiPrep (Qiagen) with 4 columns according to manufacturer's instructions. Add 0.7 volumes of isopropanol to precipitate the plasmid. Spin (17000g, 30 min, 4°C) and wash pellet with 70% ethanol. Resuspend plasmid with sterile TE buffer under sterile conditions. Yield is typically 2 mg of plasmid.
Transfection	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Split Expi293F cells to 1x10⁶ cells/ml in 1L FreeStyle 293 Expression Medium. Incubate for 24 h until cells are approximately 2x10⁶ cells/ml (37°C, 150 rpm, 8% CO₂, 75% rh). 2. Add plasmid to 20mL of pre-warmed Opti-MEM at 0.5 µg/ml final concentration. 3. Add linear PEI (1 mg/ml sterile stock) to another 20mL of pre-warmed Opti-MEM at 3 µg/ml final concentration. 4. Add the mixture from Step 3 to the one in Step 2 and incubate at room temperature for 30 min. 5. Add the plasmid/PEI mixture slowly to the cells. 6. Add sodium butyrate (1 M sterile stock) to 12 mM final concentration. 7. Incubate cells at 30°C (8%CO₂/75% rh) with shaking at 150 rpm. 8. Harvest cell culture supernatant at 5 days post transfection (900g, 20 min, 4°C). 9. Filter supernatant through 0.2 µm filter.
Purification buffers	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ni IMAC W10 buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 200 mM NaCl, 10 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol 2. Ni IMAC W25 buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 200 mM NaCl, 25 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol 3. Ni IMAC elution buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 200 mM NaCl, 250 mM imidazole, 2% glycerol 4. Size exclusion chromatography elution buffer : dPBS (from ThermoFisher) 5. Ni-sepharose beads, equilibrated in Ni IMAC W10 buffer.
Purification step 1: IMAC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Add imidazole to filtered supernatant to 10 mM final concentration. 2. Add a total of 2.5 ml equilibrated Ni-sepharose beads to the cell supernatant, split into 50-ml falcon tubes. Mix by rotation for 1 hr in a cold room. 3. Spin beads/supernatant slurry (700g, 5 min, 4°C). Decant supernatant and wash beads with 100 ml W10 buffer. Repeat wash with 50 ml W10. Spin again and transfer beads to gravity column in a cold room. 4. Wash column with 25 ml W25.

	<p>5. Elute protein with 1x 10 ml elution buffer, followed by 2x5 ml elution buffer. Analyse the EB fractions by SDS-PAGE and determine the protein yield using the Bradford assay. Pool elution fractions containing protein.</p>
<p>Purification step 2: Size Exclusion Chromatography</p>	<p>1. Concentrate pooled IMAC elution fractions to 1 ml using a centrifugal concentrator with the appropriate MWCO.</p> <p>2. Perform SEC on a HiLoad Superdex S200 HR 16/60 column, equilibrated in DPBS, at 1 ml/min.</p> <p>3. Analyse fractions by SDS-PAGE. Pool fractions containing protein of desired purity and concentrate to 1-5 mg/ml, as measured by UV spectroscopy.</p> <p>4. Snap-freeze aliquots in thin-walled PCR tubes in liquid N₂, and store at -80°C.</p>

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